

Rewilding of the Ribeira Das Vinhas in Cascais, Portugal

About this brief

This brief presents the results of a flood damage modelling approach applied to the Ribeira das Vinhas catchment area in the Municipality of Cascais in Portugal, in order to evaluate the economic value of nature restoration interventions.

Results showed that nature-based solutions can deliver economic advantages while generating broader social benefits: NbS in Cascais helped reduce displaced population by flooding by 60% and cut flood-related damages by 43%.

These results were complemented by an expert survey which reported positive changes across all assessed ecosystem services, especially recreational value and ecological quality.

Context

Cascais is a coastal municipality of approximately 210,000 inhabitants located in western Portugal, covering an area of about 30 km². Its territory hosts a rich biodiversity, also recognised by UNESCO, and attracts international tourism every year.

Tourism represents the leading economic sector in the area, contributing around one third of the municipality's income. Favourable climatic conditions and the minimisation of climate change impacts are therefore essential to sustain the local tourism-based economy.

This economic model is increasingly threatened by climate-related risks, including floods, wildfires, and the growing occurrence of heatwaves. In particular, the Ribeira das Vinhas catchment area is identified as a high flood-risk hotspot, posing a significant threat to surrounding densely urbanised areas and nearby agricultural zones.

To reduce flood risk, the Municipality of Cascais launched in 2017 a large-scale catchment restoration project, leveraging the potential of Nature-based Solutions. The initiative covered approximately 1,000 hectares and included the restoration of river buffers, the creation of ponds and retention basins, the integration of hybrid grey-green engineering elements to establish ecological corridors, and the remeandering of the river to slow water flows.

To assess the value generated by restored nature in the area, Invest4Nature estimated the reduction in flood-related damages resulting from the intervention in terms of economic damages to the building and population exposed. In addition, a qualitative assessment of ecosystem service provision was conducted to capture changes in local stakeholder perceptions following the restoration effort.

Digital version: Staccione, A. et al. (2026) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18310762>

Assessment Methods and Data

Flood Risk Modelling

Flood-related damages were estimated using a modelling approach that compares flood hazard maps before and after the restoration interventions. The analysis was conducted for a modelled flood event with a 100-year return period, considering conditions both before and after the intervention.

Two modelling tools were used to produce flood hazard maps: HEC-HMS and HEC-RAS. HEC-HMS simulated river discharge by generating hydrographs from precipitation events and a high-resolution Digital Terrain Model, which were then used as inputs to HEC-RAS to map flood extent and inundation depth. The HEC-RAS simulations were complemented by the Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND) method, a terrain-based approach that supports reliable inundation mapping where data availability is limited.

Additional material

- ▶ Staccione, A. et al., 'Economic assessment of the rewilding of Riveira das Vinhas in Cascais, Portugal'. Invest4Nature case study documentation [based on D2.2 & D3.1] <https://10.5281/zenodo.18376807>

Damage and Exposure Reduction

A depth-damage function was used to link flood hazard magnitude with building-related damages and population exposure. Changes in the expected annual damages to buildings and in the annual population exposed to flooding were used as proxies for the value generated by the nature restoration to the Municipality of Cascais.

Ecosystem services survey

An online survey combining multiple-choice, ordinal-scale, and location-mapping questions was conducted to support the validation of the modelling results. Participants, including municipal experts, were asked to indicate whether they had observed changes in ecosystem service provision following the restoration intervention. The services considered included climate regulation, water regulation, recreation, biodiversity, and habitat provision. In addition, information on the direction and intensity of observed changes, as well as respondents' confidence levels, were collected.

Flood risk mapping

The flood risk modelling produced flood depth maps for conditions before and after the restoration, using 2010 and 2024 as reference periods, respectively. The maps show that catchment restoration led to a significant reduction in both flood extent and flood depth, with outcomes also influenced by the geomorphological characteristics of the territory.

The charts show flood depth maps before (a) and after (b) restoration, based on a 100-year return period event. Model produced flood extents consistent with the official Cascais plans (c) from Câmara Municipal de Cascais, 2015, 2024

Building damages

Flood-related damage maps show that buildings most affected by flood events are primarily concentrated in the downtown area and in the built-up zones along the upstream sections of the river. Expected annual damages decreased from €110,000 in 2010 to €62,000 in 2024, corresponding to a 43% reduction in flood-related damages.

Population exposed

Population exposure maps show a significant decline and reclassification in exposure severity following the restoration intervention. The total affected population decreased by approximately 9%, while the share of people expected to be displaced annually decreased by 60%, with these individuals reclassified as only slightly affected. The number of moderately affected individuals declined by 18%, contributing to a reduction in expected annual population exposure from 130 people in 2010 to 118 in 2024.

Ecosystem service perceptions

The survey captured the perceptions of nine experts from the Municipality of Cascais regarding improvements in a range of ecosystem services due to the large-scale nature-based solutions implemented. Ecosystem services assessed included climate regulation, resilience, recreation, habitats and biodiversity. Most locations where changes were reported were situated along the Ribeira das Vinhas, although some observations were also recorded in nearby urban zones. In general, positive changes were reported for all five ecosystem services. Recreation was the most frequently selected service, reflecting the use of the restored areas for leisure activities. Habitat received the fewest responses, while resilience - understood as the capacity of Cascais to maintain its functionality during flood events - was also perceived positively.

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The economics of nature-based solutions

Invest4Nature

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